

The Future Face of the Last Frontier

Boreal Forest Resilience to Global Change

Supplementary Figures

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Chapter 2

Northern expansion is not compensating for southern declines in North American boreal forests

Figure S2.1 Simulated tree cover distribution and area change of North American boreal forests based on remote sensing time series. **a** Simulated geographical distribution range of tree presence for the years 2000 and 2019. Tree presence for the year 2000 was simulated through binomial distributions using actual mean tree cover observations along latitudinal gradients (i.e. standardised boundary distances). Tree presence for the year 2019 was simulated using observed tree cover trends over the entire 20-year period. Black horizontal lines represent the southern and northern boreal biome boundaries based on Gauthier *et al.* (2015)(Gauthier *et al.*, 2015). Purple lines show the position where these boundaries would be in 2019 based on the same tree distribution quantiles (see Supplementary discussion). **b** Tree cover for the years 2000 and 2019 and associated area change based on simulated data in (A).

Figure S2.2 Tree cover around the southern and northern boreal biome boundaries. Tree cover is expressed as means for each data point for the years 2000-2002. The band around each boundary extends to both sides by 120km. Tree cover at the easternmost and westernmost boreal biome were excluded, as the biome boundaries curve towards each other which makes a distinction between boundaries impossible.

Figure S2.3 Changes in tree cover distributions of the northern and southern boreal biome. Distributions are shown for the northern (a) and southern (b) boundary between the periods 2000-2002 and 2017-2019.

Figure S2.4 Changes in the relative proportion of tree cover classes along boreal biome boundaries. Changes are shown for the periods 2000-2002 and 2017-2019 and for the northern and southern boundary. Tree cover is expressed in bins of 5%. Change in proportions is expressed as relative change based on the proportions for the period 2000-2002.

Figure S2.5 Latitudinal displacement of tree cover classes. Shifts are shown for the periods 2000-2002 and 2017-2019 along the northern and southern boreal biome boundary. Displacement is based on the mean change in latitudes of each tree cover class between periods. Tree cover classes are expressed in 5% bins.

Figure S2.6 Mean tree cover changes 2000-2019 across Canadian ecozones and Alaska. Tree cover changes are shown for different disturbance types and timing. 'All' shows tree cover changes irrespective of disturbance. Tree cover changes were averaged based on sample plots within each ecozone. Zone labels: AL = Alaska, AH = Atlantic Highlands, BC = Boreal Cordillera, BP = Boreal Plain, BS = Boreal Shield, HP = Hudson Plains, MC = Montane Cordillera, SA = Southern Arctic, TC = Taiga Cordillera, TP = Taiga Plain, TS = Taiga Sield, Tundra C = Tundra Cordillera.

Figure S2.7 Tree cover changes of North American boreal forests from 2000-2019. Absolute (a) and relative (b) tree cover changes are shown for each of 12,954 sample plots along south-north transects.

Figure S2.8 Principal component analysis of sample plots. The following variables are shown as vectors: mean tree cover (mean TC), boundary distance (SBD), elevation, mean annual temperatures (MAT), mean annual precipitation (MAP) and trends of temperature and precipitation over two periods (1980-2019 and 2000-2019). Point colours represent the direction of tree cover change: no significant trend, tree cover gains and tree cover losses. Significance terms were calculated from a Mann-Kendall-test using the 'zyp' package in R(Bronaugh and Werner, 2019).

Figure S2.9 Relationships between absolute tree cover (TC) change 2000-2019 across North American boreal forests and environmental conditions: **a** Mean tree cover 2000-2019, **b** elevation, **c** mean annual temperatures (MAT), **d** mean annual precipitation (MAP), **e** change in MAT 1980-2019, **f** change in MAP 1980-2019, **g** change in MAT 2000-2019 and **h** change in MAP 2000-2019. Relationships are shown for different disturbance categories (colours). Lines represent model fits \pm standard errors around the fit from generalised additive mixed-effects models. Each predictor of tree cover change was included in a separate model due to correlations between predictors. Transects were used as random effects in the models. Additionally, tree cover change was fitted by disturbance type and assuming an exponential spatial correlation structure. Fitted model lines including raw data points are shown in Figure S2.18. Absolute tree cover change was calculated through a Theil-Sen's slope estimation. Standardised boundary distance represents the distance to the southern and northern boreal biome boundary, i.e. -1 = South (S), 0 = Interior (I), 1 = North (N). Boundaries were derived from Gauthier et al. 2015 (Gauthier et al., 2015). Climatic variables were taken from the ERA5 Monthly Averaged data set and cover the period 1980-2019 (2000-2019 for recent climate change trends).

Figure S2.10 Relationships between relative tree cover (TC) change 2000-2019 across North American boreal forests and environmental conditions: (A) standardised boundary distance, (B) mean tree cover 2000-2019, (C) elevation, (D) mean annual temperatures (MAT), (E) mean annual precipitation (MAP), (F) change in MAT 1980-2019, (G) change in MAP 1980-2019, (H) change in MAT 2000-2019 and (I) change in MAP 2000-2019. Relationships are shown for different disturbance categories (colours). Lines represent model fits \pm standard errors around the fit from generalised additive mixed-effects models. Each predictor of tree cover change was included in a separate model due to correlations between predictors. Transects were used as random effects in the models. Additionally, tree cover change was fitted by disturbance type and assuming an exponential spatial correlation structure. Fitted model lines including raw data points are shown in Figure S2.19. Relative tree cover change was calculated through a Theil-Sen's slope estimation method and is in relation to mean tree cover across the study period. Standardised boundary distance represents the distance to the southern and northern boreal biome boundary, i.e. -1 = South (S), 0 = Interior (I), 1 = North (N). Boundaries were derived from Gauthier et al. 2015 (Gauthier et al., 2015). Climatic variables were taken from the ERA5 Monthly Averaged data set and cover the period 1980-2019 (2000-2019 for recent climate change trends).

Figure S2.11 Spatial extent and occurrences of wildfire and timber harvest between 2000 and 2019 in relation to boreal boundaries. **a** Mean relative extent of sample plots which were disturbed. For each disturbance type, the extent is given for the most recent disturbance and accumulated for all disturbances since 2000. Extents are running means of binned boundary distances. **b** Accumulated number of sample plots disturbed by wildfire and timber harvest for each year between 2000-2019. Occurrences are summarised over binned boundary distances. Years are years of the largest and most recent disturbance recorded within sample plots.

Figure S2.12 Sampling design with sample plots located along south-north transects across North America. Panels A-C show transects and sample plots with increasing spatial detail. Background colours represent MODIS tree cover estimates for the year 2019.

Figure S2.13 Occurrences of wildfire and timber harvest across the Canadian boreal biome based on the CanLaD disturbance dataset. The black line represents the biome extent. The yellow grids are sample plots within the biome we used in our study.

Figure S2.14 Overview of spatial data used in the analysis: **a** Tree cover, **b** land cover, **c** ecozones, **d** elevation, **e** mean annual temperature, **f** mean annual precipitation and **g** Disturbances.

Figure S2.15 Variogram of tree cover trends. Variances were calculated for 10,000 random points across the North American boreal forests and binned into 100 distance groups (blue points). The bold line represents a fitted exponential variogram function. Dashed lines show the sill of maximum variance, the range at which variances and thus autocorrelated effects level off, and the nugget (the intrinsic variance for distances of 0, lower horizontal line).

Figure S2.16 Tree cover changes between 2000-2019 separated by disturbance type. Absolute (a) and relative (b) tree cover changes are shown for each of 12,954 sample plots and for each disturbance type.

Figure S2.17 Relations between tree cover change and land cover type along the southern and northern boreal forest biome boundaries. Relationships are shown for absolute (a) and relative (b) tree cover changes. Plots are separated by six land cover types and include the values from sample plots and fitted lines. Colours represent different disturbance types.

Figure S2.18 Relationships between absolute tree cover (TC) change 2000-2019 across North American boreal forests and environmental conditions. The model fit lines and environmental variables are the same as in Figure S2.10. Plots are separated by disturbance type and include the values from sample plots (grey points).

Figure S2.19 Relationships between relative tree cover (TC) change 2000-2019 across North American boreal forests and environmental conditions. The model fit lines and environmental variables are the same as in Figure S2.11. Plots are separated by disturbance type and include the values from sample plots (grey points).

Table S2.1 Area extent and proportion of fires and timber harvests within the Canadian boreal biome and the sample plots used in our study. The total area represents the area of the entire Canadian boreal biome and the sample plots. The proportion of disturbances within our sample plot is very similar to that of the entire Canadian biome.

	Canadian boreal	Sample plots
	Area (ha)	
Fire	58,633,211	1,917,950
Harvest	15,877,704	545,202
Total	529,482,711	17,251,036
	Proportion (%)	
Fire	11.1	11.1
Harvest	3.0	3.2

Table S2.2 Description and details of data sets on tree cover estimates and environmental variables.

Data set	Time period	Temporal resolution	Spatial resolution
MODIS VCF version 6 fractional tree cover	2000-2019	annual	250m
Copernicus global landcover map (GLC) version 2.0.2	2015	na	100m
ECMWF Re-analysis (ERA) version 5 monthly averaged climate data	1980-2019 and 2000-2019	monthly	0.25°
USGS Global Multi-resolution Terrain Elevation Data	2010	na	~250m
Canada Landsat Disturbance (CanLaD) including wildfire and timber harvest	1985-2019	annual	30m
Monitoring Trends in Burn Severity (MTBS)	1985-2019	annual	30m

Table S2.3 Reclassification of land cover classes from the Copernicus global land cover map (Marcel Buchhorn et al., 2019) to 14 classes for this study.

Original class names	New class names
No input data available	No data
Shrubs	Shrubs
Herbaceous vegetation	Non-woody
Cultivated and managed vegetation/agriculture (cropland)	Crops
Urban / built up	Urban
Bare / sparse vegetation	Bare
Snow and Ice	Snow and Ice
Permanent water bodies	Water
Herbaceous wetland	Wetland
Moss and lichen	Non-woody
Closed forest, evergreen needle leaf	Needleleaf
Closed forest, evergreen, broad leaf	Broadleaf
Closed forest, deciduous needle leaf	Needleleaf
Closed forest, deciduous broad leaf	Broadleaf
Closed forest, mixed	Mixed forest
Closed forest, unknown	Unknown forest
Open forest, evergreen needle leaf	Needleleaf
Open forest, evergreen broad leaf	Broadleaf
Open forest, deciduous needle leaf	Needleleaf
Open forest, deciduous broad leaf	Broadleaf
Open forest, mixed	Mixed forest
Open forest, unknown	Unknown forest
Open sea	Ocean

Chapter 3

Boreal forests are heading for an open state

Figure S3.1 Tree cover distribution and change in North American boreal forests. Each panel represents distributions or change within a tree cover-temperature space. Tree cover is shown in ranges of 1%. Temperatures are mean annual temperatures 2000-2020 and are shown in ranges of 0.5°C. **A** Observed probability densities of tree cover in the year 2000. **B** Tree cover change between 2000 and 2020. The dashed line marks zero change and thus indicates potential tree cover states. **C** Expected probability densities of tree cover in the year 2100. Tree cover was simulated from the initial values in 2000 using tree cover changes 2000-2020. The dashed line is the line of zero change around which tree cover distributions are expected. **D** Expected probability densities of tree cover in the year 2100 including observation noise.

Figure S3.2 Tree cover distribution and change in Eurasian boreal forests. Each panel represents distributions or change within a tree cover-temperature space. Tree cover is shown in ranges of 1%. Temperatures are mean annual temperatures 2000-2020 and are shown in ranges of 0.5°C. **A** Observed probability densities of tree cover in the year 2000. **B** Tree cover change between 2000 and 2020. The dashed line marks zero change and thus indicates potential tree cover states. **C** Expected probability densities of tree cover in the year 2100. Tree cover was simulated from the initial values in 2000 using tree cover changes 2000-2020. The dashed line is the line of zero change around which tree cover distributions are expected. **D** Expected probability densities of tree cover in the year 2100 including observation noise.

Figure S3.3 Tree cover distribution and change of global boreal forests under forest management. Forests with any sign of management activity, such as logging or replanting were considered. Each panel represents distributions or change within a tree cover-temperature space. Tree cover is shown in ranges of 1%. Temperatures are mean annual temperatures 2000-2020 and are shown in ranges of 0.5°C. **A** Observed probability densities of tree cover in the year 2000. **B** Tree cover change between 2000 and 2020. The dashed line marks zero change and thus indicates potential tree cover states. **C** Expected probability densities of tree cover in the year 2100. Tree cover was simulated from the initial values in 2000 using tree cover changes 2000-2020. The dashed line is the line of zero change around which tree cover distributions are expected. **D** Expected probability densities of tree cover in the year 2100 including observation noise.

Figure S3.4 Tree cover distribution and change of unmanaged global boreal forests. Only forests without any sign of human intervention were considered. Each panel represents distributions or change within a tree cover-temperature space. Tree cover is shown in ranges of 1%. Temperatures are mean annual temperatures 2000-2020 and are shown in ranges of 0.5°C. **A** Observed probability densities of tree cover in the year 2000. **B** Tree cover change between 2000 and 2020. The dashed line marks zero change and thus indicates potential tree cover states. **C** Expected probability densities of tree cover in the year 2100. Tree cover was simulated from the initial values in 2000 using tree cover changes 2000-2020. The dashed line is the line of zero change around which tree cover distributions are expected. **D** Expected probability densities of tree cover in the year 2100 including observation noise.

Figure S3.5 Tree cover distribution and change of burnt global boreal forests. Only forests that burned between 2000-2020 were considered. Each panel represents distributions or change within a tree cover-temperature space. Tree cover is shown in ranges of 1%. Temperatures are mean annual temperatures 2000-2020 and are shown in ranges of 0.5°C. **A** Observed probability densities of tree cover in the year 2000. **B** Tree cover change between 2000 and 2020. The dashed line marks zero change and thus indicates potential tree cover states. **C** Expected probability densities of tree cover in the year 2100. Tree cover was simulated from the initial values in 2000 using tree cover changes 2000-2020. The dashed line is the line of zero change around which tree cover distributions are expected. **D** Expected probability densities of tree cover in the year 2100 including observation noise.

Figure S3.6 Tree cover distribution and change of unburnt global boreal forests. Only forests that were unburnt between 2000-2020 were considered. Each panel represents distributions or change within a tree cover-temperature space. Tree cover is shown in ranges of 1%. Temperatures are mean annual temperatures 2000-2020 and are shown in ranges of 0.5°C. **A** Observed probability densities of tree cover in the year 2000. **B** Tree cover change between 2000 and 2020. The dashed line marks zero change and thus indicates potential tree cover states. **C** Expected probability densities of tree cover in the year 2100. Tree cover was simulated from the initial values in 2000 using tree cover changes 2000-2020. The dashed line is the line of zero change around which tree cover distributions are expected. **D** Expected probability densities of tree cover in the year 2100 including observation noise.

Figure S3.7 Tree cover-dependent process noise across temperature ranges. Each panel represent a temperature range of 0.5°C between -14°C and 6°C.

Figure S3.8 Tree cover-dependent observation noise across temperature ranges. Each panel represent a temperature range of 0.5°C between -14°C and 6°C.

Figure S3.9 Comparison of observed and simulated tree cover 2000-2020. Observed and simulated tree cover are shown for two time periods 2000-2004 and 2015-2020 across temperature ranges.

Figure S3.10 Relationship between tree cover and forest aboveground biomass. Relationships are shown for **A** North America and **B** Eurasia for the year 2018. The solid line represents the fit of an exponential model (model details are shown in Table S3.2). Grey data points are a random subset of 10,000 data points for better visualisation.

Figure S3.11 Validation of tree cover trend models through known models. Tree cover time series were created using **A** an Allee effect model with a threshold of 10%, **B** an Allee effect model with a threshold of 30% and **C** a logistic growth model with Allee effect. Tree cover was simulated over 21 years with stochastic noise. Grey points represent simulated data points from the models. Red lines represent the models without noise, black lines are model fits based on our approach. Points in green are points in Allee effect models that initially were below the threshold (dashed line) but moved beyond it after 21 years. Purple points were initially above the threshold but moved below it after 21 years. Note that points close to initial tree cover of 0% are more likely to have positive trends and may thus move beyond the Allee threshold when the threshold is low. This ‘bends’ the fitted black line upwards and thus disguises the Allee effect.

Figure S3.12 Estimated process and observation noise across tree cover gradient from Allee-effect models. Tree cover was created through an Allee-effect model based on Equation S6 with $C = 30\%$, $K = 80\%$, process noise = 3 and observation noise = {0,1,2,3}. **A-D** Estimated process noise fitted through Equation S4 (points) with varying model observation noise. **E-H** Estimated observation noise across varying model observation noise. The red line indicates the true process or observation noise in the model. Black lines are additive model fits.

Figure S3.13 Projected probability densities of tree cover in the year 2100 for combinations of different process and observation noise. Probability densities are shown across temperature gradients. The orange dashed line is the line of zero tree cover change around which tree cover distributions are expected. Process noise of 0.58 and observation noise of 8.7 are the measured median noise in the observed MODIS tree cover data. Model fitting and simulations were applied to all observed data across the global boreal biome.

Figure S3.14 Fire probability across the boreal biome. Fire probability is expressed as relative burnt area along the tree cover gradient. Dashed lines represent the expected range of tree cover by 2100.

Figure S3.15 Relative forest aboveground biomass change between 2000 and 2100. Biomass changes are shown for **A** North America and **B** Eurasia. Each bar represents the biomass change per temperature range. Error bars represent standard errors.

Figure S3.16 Representativeness of tree cover distributions within sample points compared to total boreal biome. Distributions of tree cover are expressed as relative area proportions for Eurasia and North America within **A** sample points and **B** the entire boreal biome.

Figure S3.17 Frequency distributions of mean annual temperatures within global boreal forests. Temperatures are separated in bins of 0.5°C and are shown for each continent (bars) and for the entire biome (black line). The red horizontal line represents the temperature range used in this study.

Figure S3.18 Standard deviations of tree cover with increasing time steps. Colours represent groups of initial tree cover values. Points are standard deviations of tree cover for each group for the following 1-10 years (Δt). Lines are model fits based on the square root of Δt . Panels separate tree cover groups into groups of 10% tree cover.

Figure S3.19 Comparison of expected tree cover distributions in 2100 for different assumptions of model noise. A The expected tree cover where noise is fitted on different temperature bins. **B** The expected tree cover where we used a general noise function, fitted on all data points. Tree cover was simulated from the initial values in 2000 using tree cover changes 2000-2020. The dashed line is the line of zero change around which tree cover distributions are expected. Probability densities in both panels do not include observation noise.

Table S3.1 Details on data sets used in this study.

Name	Source	Time period	Temporal resolution	Spatial resolution	Pre-processing
Boreal forest boundary	Delineation based on Gauthier <i>et al.</i> 2015	na	na	na	No pre-processing
Tree cover time series	MODIS Vegetation Continuous Field Collection 6	2000-2020	annual	250m	No pre-processing
Land cover classes	Copernicus Global Land Cover Map	2015	na	100m	We matched the spatial resolution with that of tree cover data (250 m) by resampling using the nearest neighbour method in ArcPro, version 2.8.3.
Climate data - Mean annual temperature and mean annual precipitation	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecast re-analysis (ERA5)	2000-2020	monthly	0.25 decimal degrees (~21 km)	We extracted monthly surface temperatures and monthly precipitation expressed as average daily precipitation between 2000 and 2020. We converted temperatures into °C and calculated the mean annual temperature over the entire period 2000-2020. We converted precipitation to total monthly precipitation using the daily value provided. We then summed the monthly precipitation across each year and calculated the mean annual precipitation over all years 2000-2020.
Predicted mean annual temperatures	EC-Earth3-Veg-LR model	2020-2100	monthly	1.25 decimal degrees (~110km)	We extracted temperature predictions for scenario SSP3-7.0 as an intermediate carbon mitigation scenario. We calculated mean annual temperatures in °C for each year 2020-2100.
Forest fires	MODIS Burned Area	2000-2020	irregular	250m	We merged all available data within our study period to map the locations and years of each detected fire.
Forest management	Global forest management dataset version 3	2015	na	100m	The map depicts categories of managed and unmanaged forest areas. We matched the spatial resolution with that of tree cover data (250 m) by resampling using the nearest neighbour method in ArcPro, version 2.8.3. We then reclassified areas as 'Unmanaged' which did not have a management category or were classified as '11 - Naturally regenerating forest without any signs of human activities'. All other forest management classes were defined as 'Managed'.
Forest aboveground biomass	European Space Agency Biomass Climate Change Initiative version 3	2010, 2018	na	250m	We matched the spatial resolution with that of tree cover data (250 m) by resampling using the nearest neighbour method in ArcPro, version 2.8.3.

Table S3.2 Representativeness of sample points for total boreal biome. Proportions of burnt and unburnt areas, as well as forest management classifications are compared for North America and Eurasia between sample points and the total boreal biome.

Region	Management	Samples	Biome	Samples	Biome
		Area (ha)	Proportion (%)		
Fire					
Eurasia	Unburnt	5,768,931	1,420,562,537	92.3	91.5
Eurasia	Burnt	481,069	132,100,313	7.7	8.5
North America	Unburnt	5,886,425	641,091,982	94.2	94.4
North America	Burnt	363,575	38,221,306	5.8	5.6
Forest Management					
Eurasia	Unmanaged - Unclassified	1,968,256	457,772,471	31.5	29.5
Eurasia	Unmanaged - Naturally regenerating	3,079,269	763,896,796	49.3	49.2
Eurasia	Managed - Naturally regenerating	1,059,363	290,014,477	16.9	18.7
Eurasia	Managed - Planted forests	140,288	40,123,511	2.2	2.6
Eurasia	Managed - Agroforestry	2,825	855,594	0.0	0.1
North America	Unmanaged - Unclassified	2,207,438	223,441,395	35.3	32.9
North America	Unmanaged - Naturally regenerating	3,384,044	373,586,624	54.1	55.0
North America	Managed - Naturally regenerating	650,356	81,297,165	10.4	12.0
North America	Managed - Planted forests	8,150	987,047	0.1	0.1
North America	Managed - Agroforestry	13	1,059	0.0	0.0

Table S3.3 Biomass models based on tree cover in North America and Eurasia. Model fit is based on an exponential function between tree cover and biomass of the year 2018.

North America	Estimate	SE	t	p
Intercept	-135.6	0.19	-725	2.00E-16
exp(Tree cover 2018/100)	137.0	0.13	1017	2.00E-16
adjusted R ²	0.51			
Eurasia				
Intercept	-153.4	0.16	-958	2.00E-16
exp(Tree cover 2018/100)	157.1	0.12	1352	2.00E-16
adjusted R ²	0.65			

Chapter 4

Stem mortality, productivity and climate determine forest recovery after insect outbreaks

Figure S4.1 Distribution of observed defoliation intensities and mortalities. Distributions are shown for the full dataset ($n = 332$).

Figure S4.2 Principal component analysis (PCA) of dominant groundcover species. Dominant plant species were recorded in 11 quadrats within each study transect ($n = 332$). The total number of recorded species per transect were put in the PCA. The first principal component aligns with the dominance of *Empetrum nigrum* at positive scores and either dominance of the grass species *Avenella flexuosa* or the forb species *Cornus suecica* at negative scores. The scores of the first principal component were used as groundcover composition in the modelling process. Only the most dominant plant species are labelled.

Figure S4.3 Correlation plot of predictor variables. Pearson correlation coefficients are shown as numbers and associated colours. Only significant correlations are shown. Correlations of ≥ 0.5 (black borders) have been substituted with each other in the model building process. Abbreviations: GS = growing season.

Figure S4.4 Relationships and model fit of stem mortality and predictor variables. Each panel row shows the relationship between stem mortality and one of the predictors included in the model. The fitted lines represent the model fit for different levels of one additional other predictor (the 5%, 50% and 95% quantiles of observed values, respectively). The remaining predictors were fixed at their median values. Points are raw data points of each field transect.

Figure S4.5 Relationships and model fit of stem mortality and predictor variables. Each panel row shows the relationship between stem mortality and one of the predictors included in the model. The fitted lines represent the model fit for different levels of one additional other predictor (the 5%, 50% and 95% quantiles of observed values, respectively). The remaining predictors were fixed at their median values. Points are raw data points of each field transect.

Figure S4.6 Model evaluation of stem mortality. **A** Quantile-quantile plot to check for normality of residuals. Points should be closely aligned to the line. **B** Quantile-quantile plot to check for normality of deviations of random intercepts (from random effect i.e. study site). Points should be closely aligned to the line. **C** Predicted values against residuals to check for even distribution of residuals. The blue line represents a fitted linear regression and should be as horizontal as possible. **D** Comparison of predicted and observed variances to check for model dispersion. The bars represent the distribution of variances of 2,000 model simulations. The blue bar represents the observed variance and should be centrally aligned within the simulated distributions. **E** Probability density of simulated versus observed stem mortalities. Grey lines represent the distribution of predicted stem mortalities from 2,000 model simulations. The blue line shows the observed distribution and should fall within the simulated data. **F** Semi-variogram to check for spatial autocorrelation of simulated and observed stem mortalities between transects. Grey lines show the semi-variogram for 2,000 model simulations. The blue points and line represent the observed data and should fall within the simulated data.

Figure S4.7 Relationships and model fit of basal shoot number and predictor variables. Each panel row shows the relationship between the number of basal sprouts per tree per transect and one of the predictors included in the top model. The fitted lines represent the model fit for different levels of one additional other predictor (the 5%, 50% and 95% quantiles of observed values, respectively). The remaining predictors were fixed at their median values. Points are raw data points of each field transect. Sprout numbers are shown on a logarithmic scale (+1).

Figure S4.8 Relationships and model fit of basal shoot number and predictor variables. Each panel row shows the relationship between the number of basal sprouts per tree per transect and one of the predictors included in the top model. The fitted lines represent the model fit for different levels of one additional other predictor (the 5%, 50% and 95% quantiles of observed values, respectively). The remaining predictors were fixed at their median values. Points are raw data points of each field transect. Sprout numbers are shown on a logarithmic scale (+1).

Figure S4.9 Model evaluation of shoot numbers. **A** Quantile-quantile plot to check for normality of residuals. Points should be closely aligned to the line. **B** Quantile-quantile plot to check for normality of deviations of random intercepts (from random effect i.e. study site). Points should be closely aligned to the line. **C** Predicted values against residuals to check for even distribution of residuals. The blue line represents a fitted linear regression and should be as horizontal as possible. **D** Comparison of predicted and observed variances to check for model dispersion. The bars represent the distribution of variances of 2,000 model simulations. The blue bar represents the observed variance and should be centrally aligned within the simulated distributions. **E** Probability density of simulated versus observed sprout numbers. Grey lines represent the distribution of predicted sprout numbers from 2,000 model simulations. The blue line shows the observed distribution and should fall within the simulated data. **F** Semi-variogram to check for spatial autocorrelation of simulated and observed sprout numbers between transects. Grey lines show the semi-variogram for 2,000 model simulations. The blue points and line represent the observed data and should fall within the simulated data.

Figure S4.10 Relationships and model fit of seedling number and predictor variables. Each panel row shows the relationship between the number of seedlings per transect and one of the predictors included in the top model. The fitted lines represent the model fit for different levels of one additional other predictor (the 5%, 50% and 95% quantiles of observed values, respectively). The remaining predictors were fixed at their median values. Points are raw data points of each field transect. Seedling numbers are shown on a logarithmic scale (+1).

Figure S4.11 Relationships and model fit of seedling number and predictor variables. Each panel row shows the relationship between the number of seedlings per transect and one of the predictors included in the top model. The fitted lines represent the model fit for different levels of one additional other predictor (the 5%, 50% and 95% quantiles of observed values, respectively). The remaining predictors were fixed at their median values. Points are raw data points of each field transect. Seedling numbers are shown on a logarithmic scale (+1).

Figure S4.12 Model evaluation of seedling numbers. **A** Quantile-quantile plot to check for normality of residuals. Points should be closely aligned to the line. **B** Quantile-quantile plot to check for normality of deviations of random intercepts (from random effect i.e. study site). Points should be closely aligned to the line. **C** Predicted values against residuals to check for even distribution of residuals. The blue line represents a fitted linear regression and should be as horizontal as possible. **D** Comparison of predicted and observed variances to check for model dispersion. The bars represent the distribution of variances of 2,000 model simulations. The blue bar represents the observed variance and should be centrally aligned within the simulated distributions. **E** Probability density of simulated versus observed seedling numbers. Grey lines represent the distribution of predicted seedling numbers from 2,000 model simulations. The blue line shows the observed distribution and should fall within the simulated data. **F** Semi-variogram to check for spatial autocorrelation of simulated and observed seedling numbers between transects. Grey lines show the semi-variogram for 2,000 model simulations. The blue points and line represent the observed data and should fall within the simulated data.

Figure S4.13 Relationships and model fit of living tree density and predictor variables. Each panel row shows the relationship between the number of seedlings per transect and one of the predictors included in the top model. The fitted lines represent the model fit for different levels of one additional other predictor (the 5%, 50% and 95% quantiles of observed values, respectively). The remaining predictors were fixed at their median values. Points are raw data points of each field transect. Seedling numbers are shown on a logarithmic scale (+1).

Figure S4.14 Model evaluation of living tree density. **A** Quantile-quantile plot to check for normality of residuals. Points should be closely aligned to the line. **B** Quantile-quantile plot to check for normality of deviations of random intercepts (from random effect i.e. study site). Points should be closely aligned to the line. **C** Predicted values against residuals to check for even distribution of residuals. The blue line represents a fitted linear regression and should be as horizontal as possible. **D** Comparison of predicted and observed variances to check for model dispersion. The bars represent the distribution of variances of 2,000 model simulations. The blue bar represents the observed variance and should be centrally aligned within the simulated distributions. **E** Probability density of simulated versus observed seedling numbers. Grey lines represent the distribution of predicted seedling numbers from 2,000 model simulations. The blue line shows the observed distribution and should fall within the simulated data. **F** Semi-variogram to check for spatial autocorrelation of simulated and observed seedling numbers between transects. Grey lines show the semi-variogram for 2,000 model simulations. The blue points and line represent the observed data and should fall within the simulated data.

Figure S4.15 Mean richness of soil nutrient indicator species across the spectrum of *E. nigrum* cover. Colours indicate *E. nigrum* cover, errorbars are standard errors. The presence of indicator species within 11 groundcover quadrats per transect was recorded. Richness represents the total number of indicator species per transect. Indicator species included: *Solidago virgaurea*, *Chamerion angustifolium*, *Geranium* spp., *Trollius europeaus*, *Filipendula ulmaria*, *Alchemilla* spp., any ferns.

Figure S4.16 *E. nigrum* cover in areas of presence and absence of nutrient indicator species. Presence means the occurrence of any indicator species in any of the 11 groundcover quadrats per transect. A list of indicator species is provided in Table S4.3

Figure S4.17 Time series of growing season length 1980-2020. 12 random transects are shown. The red line and shaded areas indicate a linear trend and standard errors, respectively.

Figure S4.18 Conceptual model of stem mortality and forest recovery of mountain birch forests following insect defoliation events. Two versions of the model are shown: a model containing growing season (GS) climate (left) and a model containing elevation (right). Arrows indicate connections between model components based on individual mixed-effects models (for easier visualisation, only significant connections are shown). Receiving components were treated as response variables in the models. Arrow colours indicate positive (orange) and negative (red) relationships. Numbers are standardised model coefficients (\pm standard errors) from individual mixed-effects models. Both overall conceptual models were tested by pSEM. The depicted models include all sample points ($n = 332$).

Figure 4.19 Testing for bias in seedling vs. basal shoot counts. As counted seedlings close to mature living trees as basal shoots, there is a risk of bias in distinguishing the two modes of reproduction. This bias means that seedling numbers could be underestimated and basal shoot number overestimated. This potential bias may increase with the number and presence of living trees. We therefore first tested the distribution of living tree density within our transects (both in the full **A** and reduced dataset **B**, see 4.3.4 Data Analysis for details). Most transects had no or only a few living trees and thus a low chance for biased counts of seedlings and basal shoots. The relationship between seedlings and living tree density (**C**) shows that where seedlings are more likely to be corrected upwards (i.e. at higher living tree densities), seedling density was very low. A correction is unlikely to change this relationship considerably. Similarly, only a few transects had basal shoots at high tree densities (**D**). A correction downwards would have only had a minor influence on the averaged number of basal shoots per tree. The strongest influence of biased basal shoots would occur in transects of only few trees but in these transects a bias is not likely. Finally, the relationship between seedlings and basal shoots (as identified in our analysis) is not likely influenced by a potential bias in both seedling and basal shoot numbers (**E**). If we correct seedlings and basal shoots in transects of higher living tree densities (circle in **E**), this relationship may even become stronger. Our model outcome is therefore unlikely affected by a potential bias.

Table S4.1 Comparison of model versions containing growing season climate and elevation.

	AIC (climate)	AIC (elevation)	BIC (climate)	BIC (elevation)	Marginal R ² (climate)	Marginal R ² (elevation)
Stem mortality model	-789	-793	-759	-767	0.25*	0.26*
Seedling model	2060	2071	2097	2104	0.26	0.19
Basal shoot model	1118	1116	1148	1142	0.10	0.10
Living tree density model	NA	NA	NA	NA	0.34 [#]	

* pseudo-R² calculated according to Efron: $R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_i (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_i (y_i - \bar{y})^2}$

Only one model used. Therefore one R² given.

Table S4.2 Result of a generalised linear mixed-effects model of defoliation intensity (predictor) and stem mortality (response). A beta-distributed residual distribution was assumed. 298 transects were included in the model. Landscape block was considered as a random effect.

	Coefficient	SE	z-value	p-value
(Intercept)	2.09	0.09	23.12	<0.001
Defoliation	0.14	0.07	2.05	0.04

Table S4.3 List of plant species defined as indicator species for nutrient-richer sites.

Species names	
Scientific	English
<i>Solidago virgaurea</i>	Goldenrod
<i>Chamerion angustifolium</i>	Rosebay Willowherb/ Fireweed
Other tall forbs (e.g. <i>Geranium</i> , <i>Trollius europaeus</i> , <i>Filipendula</i> <i>ulmaria</i>)	Geranium/ Cranesbills, Globeflower
Tall ferns (e.g. <i>Matteuccia</i> <i>struthiopteris</i> , <i>Dryopteris filix-</i> <i>mas</i>)	Ostrich fern, male fern
Small ferns (<i>Phegopteris</i> <i>connectilis</i> , <i>Gymnocarpium</i> <i>dryopteris</i>)	Beech fern, oak fern

Supplementary references

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